

Preliminary Analysis of Critical Boron Concentration Using a Fully Convolutional Network Regression Model

Shigeki Shiba^{1,*}

¹Nuclear Regulation Authority of Japan, Tokyo, Japan

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804082

ABSTRACT

In light water reactor (LWR) transient analyses that utilize deterministic simulation codes, best-estimate-plus-uncertainty (BEPU) approaches can enhance the accuracy from these simulations by incorporating uncertainty quantification. However, achieving precise uncertainty quantification through stochastic sampling-based methods can be computationally costly. Accordingly, exploring alternative models that replace stochastic sampling is necessary. This study proposes the quantification of key parameters in LWR steady-state analyses using a fully convolutional neural network (FCNN) regression model within the BEPU framework. The critical boron concentration outlined in Part III of the “OECD/NEA and the U.S. NRC PWR MOX/UO₂ Core Transient Benchmark” was initially assessed using the Core Management System 5 with perturbed JENDL-5 data. Subsequently, several FCNN regression models were built using these datasets. Optimizing the hyperparameters, the some effective FCNN regression models, as determined by their root mean square error (RMSE), were applied to evaluate critical boron concentrations. The results indicated that the concentrations using each FCNN regression model were evaluated with RMSE of between 1.47% and 1.84%. Moving forward, efforts should be made to improve the accuracy of the FCNN regression models for practical applications in uncertainty analysis.

Keywords: JENDL-5, Stochastic sampling-based uncertainty analysis, fully convolutional network model

1. INTRODUCTION

In light water reactor (LWR) safety analyses, particularly regarding reactivity-initiated accidents, rapid and prompt critical transients during anticipated operational occurrences (AOOs) and design basis accident (DBA) events typically utilize best-estimate simulation codes to perform transient plant calculations incorporating reactivity feedback from detailed core models. In addition, uncertainty quantification within best-estimate simulation codes is crucial for addressing gaps in measurement data, such as those related to rod ejection transient phenomena. As a result, best-estimate-plus-uncertainty (BEPU) approaches enhance the accuracy from simulation codes by incorporating uncertainty quantification [1]. Uncertainty sources in this context can vary widely, depending on the specific study and associated simulation code, including uncertainties originating from nuclear, manufacturing, and operational data. The LWR uncertainty analysis in the modeling benchmark project [2] has contributed significantly to our understanding of these uncertainties, identified areas needing reinforcement, and minimized the reliance on conservative safety assumptions. However, comprehensive reactor core analyses are necessary to accurately evaluate uncertainties of interest parameters. To reduce computational costs, recent studies have explored reactor core analyses employing surrogate or machine learning models [3,4]. Once a

*shiba_shigeki_c57@nra.go.jp.

high-fidelity machine learning model is developed, precisely evaluating propagated uncertainties of interest parameters using high-fidelity models with input data generated by low-fidelity models becomes possible, thereby minimizing computational costs.

This study preliminarily assesses the critical boron concentration (CBC) in Part III of the "OECD/NEA and the U.S. NRC PWR MOX/ UO_2 Core Transient Benchmark" [5] through the application of a fully convolutional neural network (FCNN) regression model [6].

This study begins by detailing the predictions made using the FCNN regression model. Section 3 discusses Part III of the OECD/NEA and U.S. NRC PWR MOX/ UO_2 Core Transient Benchmark. Section 4 describes the performance of the FCNN regression model. The final section summarizes the quantification based on the FCNN regression model.

2. PREDICTION METHODOLOGY USING FCNN REGRESSION MODEL

The prediction of interest parameters using the FCNN regression model involves two main steps: generating datasets through stochastic sampling-based uncertainty analysis and constructing the FCNN regression model.

2.1. Dataset generation for the FCNN regression model

Figure 1 illustrates the flow of transient analysis using the Core Management System 5 (CMS5) [7] with two types of perturbed binary formatted nuclear data libraries. First, perturbed binary formatted nuclear data libraries (perturbed CASMO5 libraries) were generated by NJOY2016 [8], utilizing nuclear data libraries such as JENDL-5 [9]. Here, reaction cross-section, fission yield and decay data were perturbed with covariance data. CASMO5 [10] performed burnup calculations and produced CAX files. These CAX files were then processed into binary files for SIMULATE5 [7] by CMSLINK5 [7]. SIMULATE5 then conducted reactor core analyses using the perturbed binary files and created datasets containing parameters of interest for the FCNN regression model.

Figure 1. Schematic of BEPU analysis derived from stochastic sampling-based uncertainty analysis with perturbed libraries

Figure 3. One quarter of the reactor core described by the PWR MOX/UO₂ Core Transient Benchmark [5]

Table I. Main specifications from Part III of the PWR MOX/UO₂ Core [5]

Parameter	Value
Reactor core thermal power	10 ⁻⁴ %
Total reactor core flow	15,849.4 kg/s
Reactor core average moderator temperature	560.0 K
Reactor core inlet pressure	15.5 MPa
Fuel lattice	17 × 17
Number of fuel assemblies	193

4. APPLICABILITY OF FCNN REGRESSION MODEL TO CBC

4.1. Dataset generation for the FCNN regression model

SIMULATE5 performed reactor core analyses using perturbed binary files and generated datasets (N = 1,000) with macroscopic data and CBC for the FCNN regression model. Table II lists the fundamental statistics for the parameters in the datasets generated by the stochastic sampling-based analysis. Here, two-group core averaged neutronics parameters: D_1 , D_2 , Σ_{abs1} , Σ_{abs2} , Σ_{s12} , $\nu\Sigma_1$, $\nu\Sigma_2$, ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 were evaluated using nodal neutronics perturbed parameters with perturbed nodal neutron fluxes in SIMULATE5. The relative standard deviation of CBC was 7.08%, whereas the relative standard deviations of the input parameters were all less than 1.2%. Figure 4 presents the correlation matrix for the parameters, indicating a strong correlation between CBC and both Σ_{abs2} and $\nu\Sigma_2$.

Table II. Fundamental parameter statistics for the datasets

Parameter		Mean	Standard deviation	Relative standard deviation [%]
Boron concentration	CBC (B10PM)	1318 ppm	93 ppm	7.08
Diffusion coefficient	$D_1(DF_1)$	1.40750 cm	0.00597 cm	0.42
	$D_2(DF_2)$	0.35583 cm	0.00056 cm	0.16
Macroscopic absorption cross-section	$\Sigma_{abs1}(ABS_1)$	0.01163 cm ⁻¹	0.00008 cm ⁻¹	0.67
	$\Sigma_{abs2}(ABS_2)$	0.14096 cm ⁻¹	0.00105 cm ⁻¹	0.75
Macroscopic scattering cross-section	$\Sigma_{s12}(RMV_{1-2})$	0.01652 cm ⁻¹	0.00019 cm ⁻¹	1.13
Macroscopic nu-fission cross-section	$\nu\Sigma_1(NFIS_1)$	0.00712 cm ⁻¹	0.00004 cm ⁻¹	0.62
	$\nu\Sigma_2(NFIS_2)$	0.18437 cm ⁻¹	0.00142 cm ⁻¹	0.77
Neutron flux	$\phi_1(FLUX_1)$	304333 cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	2418 cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	0.79
	$\phi_2(FLUX_2)$	35651 cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	289 cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	0.81

Figure 4. Correlation matrix of the parameters

4.2. Prediction accuracy of FCNN regression models

To predict the CBC, several FCNN regression models were built using the datasets (N = 1,000) derived from the stochastic sampling-based analysis. Table III lists the hyperparameters optimized in genetic algorithm and the associated RMSE in FCNN regression models. RMSE in a conventional linear regression model was also listed as a reference. Each FCNN regression model had an RMSE of between 1.47% and 1.84%, including the reference. In addition, Figure 5 exemplifies the prediction accuracies in the FCNN regression models (#1) and in the conventional

linear regression model with 100 test inputs. The accuracy trends through the CBC were relatively similar between the FCNN regression models (#1) and the reference.

Table III. FCNN regression models of CBC and associated RMSE

Number	Number of hidden layers (K)	Number of neurons in hidden layers (M)	Activation function (excluding output layer)	RMSE [%]
1	9	6	tanh	1.49
2	10	4	sigmoid	1.47
3	5	3	sigmoid	1.60
4	2	6	tanh	1.56
5	1	35	relu	1.66
6	3	16	sigmoid	1.64
7	9	8	tanh	1.59
8	10	60	tanh	1.77
9	3	25	relu	1.84
10	10	48	tanh	1.76
Reference	-	-	-	1.70

Figure 5. Prediction accuracy of representative FCNN regression model based on stochastic sampling analysis

5. SUMMARY

Under the BEPU framework for reactor core analyses, precise uncertainty quantification often incurs significant computational costs. Therefore, alternatives to stochastic sampling-based uncertainty analysis should be considered. Accordingly, in this study, an FCNN regression model

was proposed to predict key parameters in LWR steady-state analyses. CBCs were predicted in Part III of the "OECD/NEA and the U.S. NRC PWR MOX/UO₂ Core Transient Benchmark." These CBCs were evaluated using the CMS with the perturbed JENDL-5 in this study, leading to the development of FCNN regression models for prediction. Consequently, the FCNN regression models optimizing hyperparameters based on genetic algorithm could predict the CBCs with RMSE of between 1.47% and 1.84%, some of which were somewhat more accurate than the conventional linear regression model. Going forward, efforts should be made to enhance the accuracy of the FCNN regression models in practical applications for uncertainty analysis.

For future uncertainty analyses of AOO and DBA, the author plans to assess the FCNN ensemble regression model using input data generated by a low-fidelity model. This assessment will determine whether the uncertainties related to neutronic parameters, as derived from the FCNN ensemble regression model, are appropriate for transient analysis compared to the random sampling-based uncertainty analysis method.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the valuable reviews from F. Nagase of NRA. The author is extremely grateful for the encouragement offered by T. Sakai and K. Saito.

REFERENCES

- [1] IAEA, "International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Deterministic Safety Analysis for Nuclear Power Plants," IAEA Safety Standard Series No. SSG-2 (Rev.1), IAEA (2019).
- [2] K. Ivanov et al., "Benchmarks for Uncertainty Analysis in Modelling (UAM) for the Design, Operation and Safety Analysis of LWRs Volume I: Specification and Support Data for Neutronics Cases (Phase I)," NEA/NSC/DOC(2013)7, OECD/NEA (2013).
- [3] Y. M. Chan and J. Dufek. "Representation of Multi-group Cross Section Libraries and Flux Spectra for PWR Materials with Deep Neural Networks for Lattice Calculations," *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 208 (2024) 110746
- [4] B. Foad, R. Elzohery, and D. R. Novog. "Demonstration of Combined Reduced Order Model and Deep Neural Network for Emulation of a Time-dependent Reactor Transient," *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 171 (2022) 109017.
- [5] T. Kozlowski and T. J. Downar, "PWR MOX/UO₂ Core Transient Benchmark - Final Report," NEA/NSC/DOC, 20, OECD/NEA (2006).
- [6] M. Gevrey, I. Dimopoulos and S. Lek, "Review and Comparison of Methods to Study the Contribution of Variables in Artificial Neural Network Models," *Ecological Modelling*, 160 (2003) 249-264.
- [7] S. Vanevenhoven, T. Bahadir, G. Grandi, and J.D. Rhodes, "Advanced Three-Dimensional Multigroup Reactor Analysis Code," SSP-10/438 Rev 18, Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (2022).
- [8] R. Macfarlane, D. W. Muir, R. M. Boicourt, A. C. Kahler III, and J. L. Conlin, "The NJOY Nuclear Data Processing System, Version 2016," LA-UR-17-20093, LANL (2017).
- [9] O. Iwamoto, et al., "Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library Version 5: JENDL-5," *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, 60 (2023) 1-60.
- [10] J. D. Rhodes, R. M. Ferrer, and J. Hykes, "CASMO5 A Fuel Assembly Burnup Program User's Manual," SSP-07/431 Rev 22, Studsvik Scandpower, Inc. (2022).
- [11] MIT Sloan School of Management, "Machine Learning, Explained," [Online]. Available: <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/machine-learning-explained> (2021).